

Mucinous-Type Adenocarcinoma Arising from a Chronic anal Fistula: About 4 Cases

W. Hliwa

Gastroenterology Department of Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

H.H. Abakar ✉

Gastroenterology Department of Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

S. Sara

Gastroenterology Department of Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

A.K. Hassan

Central Laboratory of Pathological Anatomy, Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

Z. Boukhal

Gastroenterology Department of Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

F. Z. El Rhaoussi

Gastroenterology Department of Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

M. Tahiri

Gastroenterology Department of Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

F. Haddad

Gastroenterology Department of Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

A. Bellabah

Gastroenterology Department of Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

W. Badre

Gastroenterology Department of Ibn Rochd University Hospital, Casablanca, Morocco

Abstract

Perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma is a rare and aggressive tumor, most often arising from chronic anal fistulas, which makes early diagnosis difficult due to nonspecific symptoms. **Objective:** To report, through clinical cases, the clinical, therapeutic, and outcome aspects of mucinous adenocarcinoma developing on chronic anal fistulas. **Materials and methods:** A retrospective study conducted over a 3-year period (June 2022 to May 2025), including patients with mucinous adenocarcinoma arising from an anal fistula confirmed by biopsy. **Results:** Four patients with a mean age of 46.8 years presented with an anal fistula with a mean disease duration of 11.3 years. MRI revealed perianal tumor masses in continuity with the fistulous tracts. Histological examination of the fistulous tracts confirmed mucinous adenocarcinoma. All patients underwent a diverting colostomy followed by neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy. The outcome was unfavorable in two cases, with early death, highlighting the aggressive nature and poor prognosis of this disease. **Conclusion:** Mucinous perianal adenocarcinoma is aggressive and often diagnosed late. This condition should be suspected in cases of chronic fistula. Treatment must be multidisciplinary.

More Information

How to cite this article: Hliwa W, Abakar HH, Sara S, Hassan AK, Boukhal Z, El Rhaoussi FZ, Tahiri M, Haddad F, Bellabah A, Badre W. Mucinous-Type Adenocarcinoma Arising from a Chronic anal Fistula: About 4 Cases. Eur J Med Health Res, 2026;4(1):178-84.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2026.4(1).26

Keywords:

Perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma, Chronic anal fistula, Magnetic resonance imaging (MRI), Neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy, Poor prognosis.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Introduction

Perianal mucinous-type adenocarcinoma, also known as mucinous adenocarcinoma, is a rare malignant tumor with a very poor prognosis, accounting for less than 5% of anal cancers [1,2]. It is characterized by the infiltration of malignant glandular cells containing intracellular mucin. In most cases, it develops from a chronic anal fistula that has been evolving for more than ten years, with an estimated risk of malignant transformation ranging from 3% to 11% [3,4].

The aim of our work is to report, through clinical cases, the clinical, therapeutic, and evolutionary aspects of mucinous adenocarcinoma arising from chronic anal fistulas.

Materials and Methods

This is a retrospective observational descriptive study conducted over a 3-year period (June 2022 to May 2025), including patients managed for mucinous adenocarcinoma arising from an anal fistula and in whom the diagnosis was confirmed by tumor biopsy

Results

We collected four cases of mucinous (colloid-type) adenocarcinoma arising from chronic anal fistulas during the study period. The mean age of the patients was 46.8 ± 12.6 years, with two men and two women. The average duration of anal fistulas before cancer detection was 11.3 years. All patients presented with chronic proctalgia associated with a deterioration of general health, and three of them had a rapidly progressive perianal mass.

Examination of the anal margin revealed multiple fistulous openings draining pus and mucoid secretions in all patients. Among them, three had ulcerated, budding perianal masses (see Figures 1: A, B, C, D). Biopsies of the fistulous tracts and/or samples of the whitish mucoid material supported the diagnosis of colloid-type mucinous adenocarcinoma in all patients. One case showed signet-ring cells, and another displayed features of carcinomatous lymphangitis (see Figures 2: A, B).

Pelvic MRI revealed a large tumor-like mass of the anal canal in three patients and in the ischioanal space in one patient. All these formations had multiple fistulous tracts communicating with the anal canal.

Colonoscopy showed an anorectal process containing mucus arising from an anal fistula in three patients, with vaginal extension in one case.

The staging workup, consisting of a thoraco-abdomino-pelvic CT scan, showed no secondary localizations in three patients; however, one patient presented with lymph node, pulmonary, and hepatic metastases.

All patients underwent a diverting colostomy, followed by neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy after a multidisciplinary team meeting.

The clinical course was marked by the following: two of our patients died, at the 5th and 14th month respectively; one patient showed partial regression of the tumor size after chemoradiotherapy; and one patient was lost to follow-up.

Table 1: Clinical, Paraclinical, Therapeutic, and Evolutionary Aspects of Perianal Mucinous Adenocarcinoma

Observations	Case 1	Case 2	Case 3	Case 4
Age	39 years	48 years	64 years	36 years
Sex	Male	Female	Male	Female
Duration of anal fistula evolution	10 years	10 years	12 years	13 years
Main symptoms	Chronic proctalgia with deterioration of general condition	Chronic proctalgia with leucorrhea and deterioration of general condition	Chronic proctalgia with deterioration of general condition	Chronic proctalgia with an anal mass and deterioration of general condition
Examination of the Anal Margin	Polyfistulous perineum with pus and mucoid discharge (see Figure 1. A and A')	Right perianal ulcerative–proliferative mass, surrounded by multiple external fistulous openings (see Figure 1. B)	Right lateral-anal ulcerated and proliferative mass, surrounded by several external fistulous openings, with internal hemorrhoids stage III (see Figure 1. C)	Left perianal ulcerative–proliferative and abscessed mass, surrounded by several external fistulous openings (see Figure 1. D)
Histology	Mucinous adenocarcinoma with signet-ring cells (see Figure 3. A)	Invasive mucinous-type adenocarcinoma (see Figure 3. B)	Infiltrating mucinous-type adenocarcinoma with carcinomatous lymphangitis	Mucinous-type adenocarcinoma with chorion infiltration

Pelvic MRI	Multiple ano-perineal fistulas with a collection exerting a mass effect on the rectum	Polyfistulous perineum with a liquid and tissue mass fistulized to the skin and to the uterine cavity	8 cm mass in the ischioanal space, in contact with the anal margin, with suspicion of a fistulous tract connecting the mass to the anal canal	Tumor-like mass of the anal canal measuring 20 × 18 mm with multiple fistulous tracts communicating with the anal canal
Metastasis	No	Lymph node, pulmonary, and hepatic	No	No
Therapeutic Management	Diverting colostomy with chemoradiotherapy	Diverting colostomy with chemoradiotherapy	Diverting colostomy with chemoradiotherapy	Diverting colostomy with chemoradiotherapy
Evolution	Deceased after 14 months of disease progression	Deceased after 5 months of disease progression	Lost to follow-up	Partial regression of tumor size

Figure 1: Descriptive Figures of the Various Lesions Observed on Examination of the Anal Margin

Figure 2: Histological Appearance of a Mucinous (colloid-type) Adenocarcinoma

Figure 3: Endoscopic View of the Fistulous Tract

Discussion

Our study presents the clinical, radiological, therapeutic, and evolutionary characteristics of four patients with mucinous adenocarcinoma developed from a chronic anal fistula. Mucinous perianal adenocarcinoma is a rare and aggressive malignant tumor that develops in the lower third of the anal canal. It accounts for less than 5% of all anal tumors [1,2]. This condition is most often associated with a persistent or recurrent chronic anal fistula evolving for more than 10 years [3]. Malignant transformation of chronic perianal fistulas remains rare, accounting for between 3% and 11% of perianal cancers [4].

The pathogenesis of this transformation remains poorly understood. However, it has been suggested that repeated friction, prolonged chronic inflammation and recurrent episodes may induce abnormal hyperplasia

of the glandular epithelium or fistula lining, gradually leading to cancerous transformation [5]. Perianal Crohn's disease is also a recognized risk factor, although malignant degeneration in these patients remains rare [6]. Ball et al. reported that prolonged use of immunosuppressive agents and anti-TNF medications, used in the treatment of Crohn's disease, may contribute to the development of this type of cancer [7]. Furthermore, Sjö Dahl et al. observed an incidence of 0.7% of mucinous perianal adenocarcinoma in patients with Crohn's disease [8]. None of our patients had Crohn's disease.

Early diagnosis of this tumor is difficult because of its slow growth and because its clinical manifestations are often masked by symptoms typically associated with abscesses or anal fistulas. Warning signs include a long history of fistulas, the presence of a painful ulcerative–proliferative mass in the perianal region, defecation discomfort, local discharge, or mucinous drainage [9,10,11]. In contrast, common digestive symptoms associated with rectal tumors, such as bowel obstruction or rectal bleeding, are uncommon [12,13,14]. At a more advanced stage, progressive enlargement of the inguinal lymph nodes, often resistant to anti-infective treatments, may be observed [15,16].

Perianal fistulas rarely progress to a malignant lesion, leading to frequent delays in diagnosis. This justifies a high level of suspicion, particularly in patients with chronic fistulas whose shape, size, or appearance changes [17]. According to Rosser, three criteria must be met to confirm that a mucinous adenocarcinoma arises from a fistula: a fistula evolving for more than 10 years (although this threshold is debated), a tumor of the rectum or anal canal resulting from tumor spread via the fistula, and a fistula with an internal opening located in the anal canal and an external opening on the perianal skin [9]. All our patients had a chronic anal fistula evolving for more than 10 years before cancer appeared.

However, several studies have shown that this tumor may develop from fistulas with a duration of less than 10 years. A Japanese multi-institutional study reported that 37% of the 164 patients had a fistula for less than 10 years [18]. Similarly, a study conducted in an American institution found that 21% of the 14 reported cases developed within 10 years of the fistula diagnosis [19].

Imaging examinations play a key role in the diagnosis and assessment of tumor extension. Pelvic MRI is the most sensitive modality. It generally shows a hyperintense T2-weighted signal, typical of mucin, as well as the presence of a fistula between the tumor and the anal canal or rectum. It also allows detailed evaluation of perianal anatomy, local tumor extension, and lymph node involvement—mainly through

lymphatic spread—which is essential for preoperative planning [17,20,21,22]. In our study, MRI clearly demonstrated the presence of multiple fistulous tracts between the tumor and the anal canal.

Endo-anal ultrasound is also useful, as it reveals multiple hypoechoic cavities separated by thin septa, with echogenic areas corresponding to mucin lakes [23].

In at-risk patients, particularly those with Crohn's disease—approximately 20% of whom develop anal fistulas—ileocolonoscopy is recommended to rule out active inflammatory disease [24,25]. Ileocolonoscopy was normal in all our patients.

The diagnosis of mucinous adenocarcinoma relies on histopathological examination, characterized by mucin lakes representing more than 50% of the tumor and containing malignant cells. However, the predominance of mucin frequently leads to falsely negative biopsies. Therefore, in cases of strong clinical suspicion, repeated sampling is recommended, as demonstrated by the study of Okada et al., where several biopsies were negative before establishing the diagnosis [26,27,28,29]. In our cases, the initial biopsies confirmed the diagnosis.

Optimal management of perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma is based on a multidisciplinary approach combining neoadjuvant therapy, surgical resection and adjuvant treatment [12,30,31]. This strategy significantly improves clinical and oncological outcomes [10].

Surgery remains the cornerstone of treatment for this malignant entity. It is mainly based on extended local resection, which is indicated when the tumour is completely resectable, the surgical margins are negative, and the anal sphincters are preserved [12, 15, 32].

In the presence of rectal involvement, sphincter involvement, or metastases, abdominoperineal amputation (APA) combined with wide resection is recommended in order to obtain clear surgical margins [31,33].

Additionally, for patients with incomplete resection or those who decline surgery, combined chemoradiotherapy is an effective therapeutic alternative [34,12].

In contrast, for patients without lymph node metastases and with negative surgical margins, postoperative adjuvant chemotherapy is not necessary [35,36].

Other research suggests that neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy could play a key role in the management of this cancer. It could reduce tumour burden, improve resectability and thus optimise prognosis. This strategy could also prolong recurrence-free survival [31, 37]. In this regard, Hongo et al., in a study of 11 patients, reported prolonged survival in

patients who received chemoradiotherapy before surgery [38].

In our study, all patients underwent a diverting colostomy followed by neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy with the aim of performing an abdominoperineal amputation.

The prognosis appears to be poorer when the tumor exceeds 5 cm, when carcinoembryonic antigen (CEA) levels are elevated, or when lymph node or hematogenous metastases are present at the time of diagnosis [39,40]. Some studies report survival times ranging from 2 to 48 months [41]. In our series, two patients died: the first after 5 months of disease progression, and the second after 14 months.

Conclusion

Mucinous-type perianal adenocarcinoma is a rare tumor with a very poor prognosis. It should be suspected in the presence of an anal mass and/or mucinous discharge from a chronic anal fistula, which often leads to delayed diagnosis. Management relies on chemoradiotherapy and surgery.

Reference

- [1] Hanif Z, Shanmugarajah K, Middleton S. Perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma presenting as recurrent perianal sepsis. *New Horiz Clin Case Rep.* 2017;2:34.
- [2] Borpujari P, Bhargava S. Unusual presentation of mucinous adenocarcinoma in a post fistulectomy case. *Med J Armed Forces India.* 2015;71(Suppl 1):S111–S113. doi:10.1016/j.mjafi.2014.10.007.
- [3] Koizumi M, Matsuda A, Yamada T, Morimoto K, Kubota I, Kubota Y, et al. A case report of anal fistula-associated mucinous adenocarcinoma developing 3 years after treatment of perianal abscess. *Surg Case Rep.* 2023;9:159. doi:10.1186/s40792-023-01743-3.
- [4] Ilbawi AM, et al. Wide local excision of perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma. *J Clin Oncol.* 2015;33(4):e16. doi:10.1200/JCO.2014.59.7309.
- [5] Alvarez-Laso CJ, Moral S, Rodríguez D, Carrocera A, Azcano E, Cabrera A, et al. Mucinous adenocarcinoma on perianal fistula: a rising entity? *Clin Transl Oncol.* 2018;20:666–669. doi:10.1007/s12094-017-1750-y.
- [6] Kotsafti A, Scarpa M, Angriman I, Castagliuolo I, Caruso A. Fistula-related cancer in Crohn's disease: a systematic review. *Cancers (Basel).* 2021;13:1445. doi:10.3390/cancers13061445.
- [7] Ball CS, Wujanto R, Haboubi NY, Schofield PF. Carcinoma in anal Crohn's disease: discussion paper. *J R Soc Med.* 1988;81:217–219.
- [8] Sjödal RI, Myrelid P, Söderholm JD. Anal and rectal cancer in Crohn's disease. *Colorectal Dis.* 2003;5(5):490–495. doi:10.1046/j.1463-1318.2003.00481.x.
- [9] Rosser C. The relation of fistula in ano to cancer of the anal canal. *Trans Am Proctol Soc.* 1934;35:65–71.
- [10] Inoue Y, Kawamoto A, Okigami M, et al. Multimodality therapy in fistula-associated perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma. *Am Surg.* 2013;79:e286–e288.
- [11] Sierra EM, Villanueva Saenz E, Martínez PH, et al. Mucinous adenocarcinoma associated with fistula in ano: report of a case. *Tech Coloproctol.* 2006;10:51–53. doi:10.1007/s10151-006-0246-2.
- [12] Yang BL, Shao WJ, Sun GD, et al. Perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma arising from chronic anorectal fistulae: a review from a single institution. *Int J Colorectal Dis.* 2009;24:1001–1006. doi:10.1007/s00384-009-0710-3.
- [13] Ohta R, Sekikawa K, Goto M, et al. A case of perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma arising from an anorectal fistula successfully resected after preoperative radiotherapy. *Case Rep Gastroenterol.* 2013;7:219–223. doi:10.1159/000351995.
- [14] Papapolychroniadis C, Kaimakis D, Giannoulis K, et al. A case of mucinous adenocarcinoma arising in long-standing multiple perianal and presacral fistulas. *Tech Coloproctol.* 2004;8(Suppl 1):s138–s140.
- [15] Ong J, Jit-Fong L, Ming-Hian K, Boon-Swee O, Kok-Sun H, Eu KW. Perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma arising from chronic anorectal fistulae: a review from a single institution. *Tech Coloproctol.* 2007;11:34–38. doi:10.1007/s10151-007-0326-8.
- [16] Chen ZK, Chen ZH, Wu SB, et al. Malignant transformation of chronic anal fistula: clinical analysis of 6 cases. *J Chin Gen Surg.* 2006;(10):769–771.
- [17] Chand M, et al. Mucinous carcinoma of the rectum: a distinct clinicopathological entity. *Tech Coloproctol.* 2014;18:335–344. doi:10.1007/s10151-013-1093-6.
- [18] Sameshima S, Sawada T, Nagasako K. Squamous cell carcinoma of anus and carcinoma in association with anal fistula in Japan: multi-institutional registration. *J Jpn Soc Coloproctol.* 2005;58:415–421.
- [19] Gaertner WB, Hagerman GF, Finne CO, Alavi K, Jessurun J, Rothenberger DA, et al. Fistula-associated anal adenocarcinoma: good results with aggressive therapy. *Dis Colon Rectum.* 2008;51:1061–1067. doi:10.1007/s10350-008-9280-8.
- [20] Ibáñez Aguirre FJ, Erro Azcárate JM, Aranda Lozano F, et al. Mucinous adenocarcinoma on chronic perianal fistula treated by neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy and laparoscopic abdominoperineal resection. *Rev Esp Enferm Dig.* 2006;98:310–312.

- [21] Purkayastha A, Sharma N, Dutta V, et al. Mucinous adenocarcinoma of perianal region: an uncommon disease treated with neoadjuvant chemoradiation. *Transl Gastroenterol Hepatol*. 2016;1:52. doi:10.21037/tgh.2016.07.02.
- [22] Hama Y, Makita K, Yamana T, Dodanuki K. Mucinous adenocarcinoma arising from fistula in ano: MRI findings. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 2006;187:517–521. doi:10.2214/AJR.05.0011.
- [23] Gkegkes ID, Milionis V, Goutas N, Mantzoros I, Bourtzinakou AA, Stamatiadis AP. Perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma: a case report and a systematic review of the literature. *J Gastrointest Cancer*. 2024;56:6. doi:10.1007/s12029-024-01116-5.
- [24] Church J, et al. The relationship between fistulas in Crohn's disease and associated carcinoma: report of four cases and review of the literature. *Dis Colon Rectum*. 1985;28:361–366.
- [25] Ky A, et al. Carcinoma arising in anorectal fistulas of Crohn's disease. *Dis Colon Rectum*. 1998;41:992–996.
- [26] Cenac LA, Xiao P, Asarian A. Incidental discovery of mucinous adenocarcinoma from a suspected inflammatory perianal mass. *J Surg Case Rep*. 2020;2020:rjz413. doi:10.1093/jscr/rjz413.
- [27] Luo C, Cen S, Ding G, Wu W. Mucinous colorectal adenocarcinoma: clinical pathology and treatment options. *Cancer Commun (Lond)*. 2019;39:1–13. doi:10.1186/s40880-019-0361-0.
- [28] Okada K, Shatari T, Sasaki T, Tamada T, Suwa T, Furuuchi T, et al. Is histopathological evidence really essential for making a surgical decision about mucinous carcinoma arising in a perianal fistula? *Surg Today*. 2008;38:555–558. doi:10.1007/s00595-007-3653-3.
- [29] Getz SB Jr, Ough YD, Patterson RB, Kovalcik PJ. Mucinous adenocarcinoma developing in chronic anal fistula. *Dis Colon Rectum*. 1981;24:562–566.
- [30] Oh CK, et al. Long-term oncologic outcome of postoperative complications after colorectal cancer surgery. *Ann Coloproctol*. 2020;36(4):273–280. doi:10.3393/ac.2020.07.02.
- [31] Santos MD, Nogueira C, Lopes C. Mucinous adenocarcinoma arising in chronic perianal fistula: good results with neoadjuvant chemoradiotherapy followed by surgery. *Case Rep Surg*. 2014;2014:386150. doi:10.1155/2014/386150.
- [32] Anwar S, Welbourn H, Hill J, Sebag-Montefiore D. Adenocarcinoma of the anal canal: a systematic review. *Colorectal Dis*. 2013;15:1481–1488. doi:10.1111/codi.12325.
- [33] Hama Y, Makita K, Yamana T, Dodanuki K. Mucinous adenocarcinoma arising from fistula in ano: MRI findings. *AJR Am J Roentgenol*. 2006;187:517–521. doi:10.2214/AJR.05.0011.
- [34] Oberholzer K, Menig M, Kreft A, Schneider A, Junginger T, Heintz A, et al. Rectal cancer: mucinous carcinoma on MRI indicates poor response to neoadjuvant chemoradiation. *Int J Radiat Oncol Biol Phys*. 2012;82:842–848. doi:10.1016/j.ijrobp.2010.08.057.
- [35] Inoue T, Sekido Y, Ogino T, Hata T, Miyoshi N, Takahashi H, et al. Resection of anorectal fistula cancer associated with Crohn's disease after preoperative chemoradiotherapy. *Surg Case Rep*. 2023;9:197. doi:10.1186/s40792-023-01781-x.
- [36] Chrysikos D, Mariolis-Sapsakos T, Triantafyllou T, Karampelias V, Mitrousias A, Theodoropoulos G. Laparoscopic abdominoperineal resection for mucinous adenocarcinoma associated with anal fistula. *J Surg Case Rep*. 2018;2018:rjy036. doi:10.1093/jscr/rjy036.
- [37] de Souza ABP, et al. Mucinous adenocarcinoma in perianal fistula in Crohn's disease. *Int J Surg Case Rep*. 2022;95:107211. doi:10.1016/j.ijscr.2022.107211.
- [38] Hongo K, Kazama S, Sunami E, et al. Perianal adenocarcinoma associated with anal fistula: a report of 11 cases in a single institution focusing on treatment. *Int J Colorectal Dis*. 2011;26:749–754. doi:10.1007/s00384-011-1153-2.
- [39] Prasad SN, Razik A, Siddiqui F, Lal H. Mucinous adenocarcinoma arising from chronic perianal fistula mimicking horseshoe abscess. *BMJ Case Rep*. 2018;2018:bcr2017223063. doi:10.1136/bcr-2017-223063.
- [40] Marti L, Nussbaumer P, Breitbach T, et al. Perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma: a further reason for histological study of anal fistula or anorectal abscess. *Chirurg*. 2001;72:573–577.
- [41] Anthony T, Simmang C, Lee EL, et al. Perianal mucinous adenocarcinoma. *J Surg Oncol*. 1997;64:218–221.

